

Grain yield and plant characteristics of photoperiod-sensitive rices by variety and nitrogen level under shallow-deepwater conditions in north Bihar, India.

Treatment	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle wt (g)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Spikelet fertility (%)		1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain:straw ratio	Grain yield (t/ha)
					Original value	Transformed value			
Variety									
64-117 ^a (Chenab)	169	198	2.0	85.9	94.4	76.4	30.0	0.4	2.6
62-68 ^a (Kabara)	156	147	1.4	101.7	92.4	74.0	21.9	0.3	1.6
62-31 ^a (Bajara)	166	185	1.6	74.1	90.7	72.4	27.4	0.3	2.0
62-10 ^a (Barogar)	171	174	1.6	81.6	91.4	73.1	27.8	0.3	1.9
BR14 ^a (Jessaria A)	178	133	1.3	74.8	90.7	72.4	24.0	0.2	1.4
Parwapankh ^b	168	184	2.0	95.8	95.7	78.1	27.0	0.3	2.3
Akalbir ^b	199	171	1.7	100.3	94.1	76.0	28.3	0.3	1.9
S.Em. ±	4.3	8.8	0.09	3.2	—	0.54	0.41	0.02	0.14
C.D. 5%	12.3	25.2	0.26	9.2	—	1.54	1.18	0.05	0.39
Nitrogen level (kg/ha)									
					<i>Av for all varieties</i>				
0	171	176	1.61	83.4	92.5	74.4	26.7	0.3	2.0
20	172	170	1.67	93.1	92.9	74.7	27.3	0.3	2.0
40	174	165	1.69	86.7	92.8	74.6	25.3	0.3	1.9
S.Em. ±	4.8	4.2	0.08	4.0	—	0.18	0.25	0.03	0.05
C.D. 5%	ns	ns	ns	ns	—	ns	ns	ns	ns

^aSelected from local variety in parentheses. ^bLocal variety. ns = not significant.

nificantly by nitrogen levels. However, plant height tended to increase with nitrogen level. A trend toward reduction in panicle number per square meter and

grain-straw ratio with increasing levels of nitrogen was discernible. This indicates a need to evolve nitrogen-responsive varieties for shallow-

deepwater conditions.

Variety by nitrogen interaction was not significant. ■

Rice germplasm collection in North Bihar, India

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The 807 specimens from 13 districts represent a wide spectrum of tolerance for such conditions as moisture stress in early vegetative phase; waterlogging in lowland, semideep, and deep water conditions; and reactions to brown spot and rice tungro virus. Screening against stem borer, brown spot, rice tungro virus, brown planthopper, whitebacked plant-hopper, and waterlogged and deep water conditions has begun. A method to reject duplicates is being developed.

Farmers usually grow photoperiod-sensitive aman rices. Bakol, a long bold type with straw color husk and red to white pericarp, can be grown from transplanted mid-land sites to semi-deepwater (10-80 cm water depth). It tolerates submergence for a few days at the stem elongation stage.

The highly prized Basmati rice from Champaran district is a fragrant, medium slender type. Other scented types are Kamod, Tulsi manjari, Tulsi

phool, Katarni, and Baharani.

Anandi is preferred for in Champaran district for parched or popped rice (muree or murmura).

Flaked rice is more common in North Bihar. The widely grown Maricha is mildly scented and palatable. Among the high yielding varieties, Pankaj is more preferred.

Semideep and deepwater rices are direct-seeded in low-lying depressions during March-April. Varieties grown under these conditions yield only 0.5-0.6/ha. Damage is caused by stem borers, rice tungro virus, water-birds, and nocturnal animals.

Rice is grown to a maximum water depth of 5 m in Kursela (Purnea), Kanwarlake in Charia-Bariarpur (Begusarai), Satanpur-Hasanpur in Dalsingsarai (Samastipur), Kusheshwar Asthan (Darbhanga), and Barailachaur (Vaishali). Some widely grown varieties are Borogar, Salmot, Lattipakar, Darmi, Singara, Jagar, and Parwapankh.

Sathi, a cleistogamous variety, is being grown as an aus rice, followed by a second crop of aman rice. The variety is poor yielding and highly susceptible to sheath rot.

Over 80% of the area is still under tall indicas. Farmers practice late transplanting up to the middle of August. In flood affected areas, transplanting continues to late September, depending upon flood recession. Double transplanting or 60-80-day-old seedlings are used. ■

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